

SchoolFan

Scalable Citizen Science model

SchoolFan (www.schoolfan.eu) applied a citizen science project involving school teachers and their students (age 14 to 18) in the study of climate change-related fake news in Greece, France, Portugal and Spain.

3 Objectives

1. Empower teachers and their classes to report, analyse and debunk fake news related to climate change

2. Foster secondary students' digital, scientific and citizenship competences

3. Develop a scalable citizen science model that can be replicated in other contexts.

4 European countries

93 Teachers trained

31 schools

350 students reached

Steps to apply SchoolFan in your educational context

1. Situate the activity

If you are outside France, Greece, Portugal and Spain find where to place the activity in your curriculum. Find inspiration in our focus group report.

2. Training & Educational Resources

developed to train secondary school teachers and students. They can be adapted to different formal and non-formal educational contexts

3. Citizen science activity

Links to the informed consent and citizen science data collection forms - to be used as a template

4. Integration

Our best practices' report summarises our results and lesson' evaluation, improvement of the activity and repeat.

5. Evaluations

to monitor and improve process and resources

SchoolFan project (Schools against Fake News for a cooler future). ERASMUS+ 2023-1-PT01-KA220-SCH-000160782

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